

Isha Journal

Publication series of the International Students of History Association

2/94

History of Daily Life

Papers of the fifth Isha Conference
Utrecht, The Netherlands
April 4-8, 1994

Edited by Bodien Abels and Carine van Rhijn

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*Simion Costea
apr 1994 Utrecht - Olanda*

Atalanta
Houten
1994

The Isha Journal is published by the
International Students of History Association.
The aim of this publication series is to offer an
international publication possibility for history students
from all around the world including the papers
of the Annual Conferences of ISHA.

ISSN: 1023-1048

The International Student of History Association is an international,
academic, non-profit-making, independent network of students and recent graduates
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EDITORIAL

And finally, there it is ... the second issue of ISHA-Journal, containing the papers
of the fifth Annual ISHA-Conference. Due to the very high productivity of the
participants, it has been a while. Some of you may even hardly recognise their
texts, for reason that we have edited quite strictly as far as the use of English was
concerned. Still, we have always tried to follow your texts as close as possible,
though we might not always have succeeded in understanding precisely what was
meant. To those who find their papers misinterpreted: we offer our sincere
excuses.

What remains for us is to thank the following people, who spent a lot of time
working on this conference-book: first and foremost: Lidy van Roosmalen, who
managed to do the lay-out of this book, which was handed in to her as a hand-full
of unorganised floppy-discs ..., secondly, Mrs Barbara van Rhijn, for speedy
correction and a lot of moral support – Madame, many thanx! Then, our dedicated
typing-slaves Liesbeth, Cyriel and Marjolein, who, even after organising and
enduring the conference, were prepared to spend hours behind their word
processors ... Jaap Verheul for his encouragements and support of many kinds (we
still owe him a beer!). For funding and all other kinds of help, our sincere thanks
to the University of Utrecht and VIGU (Vrienden van het Instituut voor Geschie-
denis Utrecht). Without your support, it would not have been possible to make this
book.

Last but not least, thanks to all those who participated in the conference and
presented this enormous amount of papers. After all you wrote this book, and so
our editorial advise is: 'Read your book!'

The editors:
Bodien Abels
Carine van Rhijn

Utrecht, September 23, 1994

CONTENTS

EDITORIAL	III
Part I: OUTLAWS	
ANNA BRZEZINNSKA Magic at the Jagiellonian courts	3
HELENA ROGOVA Some aspects of the history of witchcraft in Western Europe in the Middle Ages	9
X SIMION COSTEA Prostitution in Braila (Rumania) at the end of the nineteenth century	12
NIINA VÄNTÄNEN Prostitution in Helsinki during the late nineteenth century	14
SARI FORSSTRÖM Prostitution in Helsinki 1908-1994 <i>The legal basis of the arrests and other control measures used by the authorities</i>	18
ANTON TANTNER Jazz youth subcultures in Nazi-Europe	22
CONSTANTIN IORDACHI The angry young men's daily life in Great Britain (late Fifties and the Sixties) <i>The gap between generations</i>	29
K.-J.C.P. DE WEERT The daily life of the cartoonist	32
AAPPO KAHONEN Attitudes towards foreigners in Finland	40
MANUEL-MARIAN DONESCU The emancipation of the gypsies in Rumania <i>Law or mentality?</i>	42
WIEBKE REDLICH & RALF STAPF Displaced persons	44
DIANA IELEJA & MARIA GOLUBEVA Political outlaws in Stuart England	52
LUKASZ KAMIŃSKI Daily life of political prisoners in Poland in the Stalinist period (1944-1956)	57
JURIS ZALÁNS Latvian baptists as outlaws under Soviet regime	60

KADRI KALLIKORM The conflict between the teutonic order and the church in late thirteenth-early fourteenth-century Livonia <i>Views from both sides and outside (a Progress Report)</i>	63
CHRISTINE PETRY Female outsiders in the Middle Ages and in early modern times	68
DAN-PETRU AVASILOAIEI Latrones – delinquency or social uprising?	72
IONUT COSTEA Living on the edge <i>Two examples</i>	76
JARI VÄISÄNEN Minority groups in Finland in the nineteenth century	78
HANNA-MARIA TARJAMO Originality and the village idiot	82
THOMASZ S. GAZAZKA Society's attitude towards mentally ill or disturbed persons in history	86
PIROSKA KISCELLI Ladies and gents with camellias <i>Tuberculosis, the plague of the nineteenth century</i>	93
Part II: BIG THINGS	
NICOLA ROETHER German emigration to the United States in the nineteenth century	103
KARSTEN C. EICHNER Unemployment in the Glasgow area <i>The Situation of the Workers in John Brown's Shipyard, Clydebank, 1930-1934</i>	106
SANDER EVERS Constantine and the battle at the Milvian bridge (312 AD)	116
VICTORIA LITOVCHENKO The fourth marriage of emperor Leo VI the Wise as a cause of religious struggle between Nicholaites and Euphimites	120
STEVEN MERTENS, MIKE SAVELKOUL, JAN VERBRUGGHE, BETTINA VOGEL, GEERT PELCKMANS & KATIA VAN DEN BERGHE Napoleon Bonaparte, a video	123
ROLF LANNDÉR Between fire and water <i>A study of people in time of war</i>	129

KATRIINA RÄMÄNEN & KATRI WALLENIUS The significance of the Napoleonic wars for Finland <i>Russian invaders in Tampere, 1808-1809</i>	132
HANNA KUUSI War as an everyday experience <i>The life of a Finnish family during 1939-1944</i>	138
STELLA PARLAND Finnish war-children 1939-1944	143
PIOTR LISOWSKI Why did people under different forms of totalitarianism submit to their fate with such humility?	147
PETER APOR The relation between death and laughter	150
Part III: HOME	
MARIA ESPERANZA CASTRO NIETO Viana do Bolo	159
JAKOVINA TVRTKU Daily life in the town and district of Pozega (Eastern Croatia) in the second half of the nineteenth century	163
ANDRIS SNE Dwelling places in the territory of Latvia during the late Iron Age	169
CLAUDIA NITU Habitat in Monteoru culture	172
FLORIN CIOSAN Aspects concerning architecture and ornamentation of border houses in Banat	178
CRISTIAN GAZDAC The implication of the roman house upon barbarian mentalities	181
GABRIEL PAUN The daily life at the royal castle Peles at Sinaia (1883-1914)	183
MIKA PERTTOLA Family life in the European city of the nineteenth century	189
TUULIKKI LAURILA A comparison between the expenses of one individual Finnish student in the middle of the 1960s and in the 1990s	193
SILVIU RAZVAN JORA Some theoretical aspects of the daily life of students	197

JOHANNES KÖLLNER	
Waste removal in Heidelberg	199
ELINA NUMMELIN & SARI SALMELA	
Household technology in Helsinki during the latter half of the nineteenth century	206
MARIUS DIACONESCU	
Women's position in Northern Transsylvania (the district of Maramures) during the fifteenth century	209
EMILIA CIUREA	
Egyptian cosmetics and toilet objects	212
KISS TÜNDE	
Mortaria from the Roman fort of Lussonium (Dunakömlöd)	217
RACHEL STRUYK	
Foundlings in Roman antiquity	221
S.D. LYTOVTCHENKO	
Roman hostages	226
Part IV: TIME	
ALEXANDER JOHANNES WAHL	
The 'Revival of the narrative method'?	
<i>Annotations</i>	231
LUCIAN JORA	
Different modalities of time-perception in daily life	
<i>Rumanians in Transsylvania in the Middle Ages</i>	235
CARMEN SHMITH	
Transylvanian Enlightenment literature	
<i>A book against superstitions</i>	239
IULIA SANA	
Wedding between tradition and everyday reality	242
ROLF DINU	
Engagement and marriage in the early nineteenth century	
in Wallachia	245
ALIN CIUPALA	
The Fun Fair, an old tradition	
<i>An example of daily life in Bucharest in the 19th century</i>	250
JAROSLAW SUCHOPLES	
Music in the everyday life of Gdansk in the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries	253
ALINA TUDOR	
Spatial and temporal horizon of the legionary 'nest'	260

MIHAI FLOREA	
Cluj – urbanism and politics	265
ADRIAN CIOROIANU	
Daily life and perception of time in the 1980s in Rumania	
<i>A day of Ion Ionescu's life</i>	268
VIRGILIU TIRAU	
The impact of advertising upon the cultural life of Cluj-Napoca	
<i>The interbellum period</i>	271
ROMEO DRULA	
Japan today	
<i>Daily life between tradition and transformation</i>	274
JEROME PENOT & CLAIRE CIVEL	
The five levels of the Parisian world	281
JOACHIM STEPHAN	
The homage to the prince-electors Albrecht Achilles at Salzwedel in 1471	289
FRANCK COUTEAU	
Daily life of the French nobility in the nineteenth century	
<i>The activities of a young noble man, Louis de Vaulchier du Deschaux, during the 1830s</i>	293
JOUKO TOSSAVAINEN	
Let's go to the hop	298
LAITINEN & MIETTINEN	
The myths of Finnish drinking habits	303
TIINA TÖRNQVIST	
Booze smuggling in Finland during the prohibition	306

PROSTITUTION IN BRAILA (Rumania) AT THE END OF THE NINETEENTH CENTURY

SIMION COSTEA (Rumania)

The history of prostitution is a new subject for Rumanian historiography. In order to investigate this we need to study documents to make generalizations possible. The present paper is an attempt to be such a study. The purpose is to analyze a document which has not been interpreted by historiography yet, a case-study which will give us a cross-section of the problem of prostitution, especially concerning venereal diseases in the town of Braila (Rumania) at the end of the nineteenth century. The document used, is a contemporary report by doctor Butarescu, chief doctor of the Hospital of Braila, which was addressed to the Romanian authorities with the purpose to encourage them to take immediate prophylactic measures against venereal diseases. In his report Dr. Butarescu offers a sociological study based on the data offered by the hospital registers, the local administration's inquiries, and his own observations. Dr. Butarescu's report is very important since the attention of the specialists for this subject was relatively rare at the end of the nineteenth century. In the period between the two World Wars, the interest for the state of prostitution in Rumania increased. Dr. Butarescu's opinion is a personal one, but does express the spirit of his epoch and milieu. In this way he represents a current of the public opinion in Rumania. The report is presented from a realistic, scientific and elitist point of view.

The Prostitution legislation in Rumania was of the regulation-type, after the French model. But at the end of the nineteenth century the legislation was far behind reality. There were two types of prostitution: one type was regulated by laws, practised in brothels and the other type was illegal prostitution which was practised in illegal brothels and in restaurants, coffeehouses, etcetera.

There were in the towns of Rumania no single, individually operating prostitutes who accosted their clients in the streets, because the mentality of the people was severely against it. An exception in this respect was Bucharest, the capital of Rumania where there were such cases.

Most of the prostitutes lived in Bucharest and in the Danube ports Braila and Galati, and this has a direct relationship with urban development and the flux of people passing through these towns. Almost half of the number of brothels

existing in Rumania (except Bucharest) were concentrated in these two ports. There was annually an average number of 120-140 legal prostitutes and over 100 illegal prostitutes at a population of 40,000 inhabitants. That is, one prostitute per 166 inhabitants, which indicates a higher number of prostitutes than the average number in 7 big towns in England. In the following 25 years their number increased as the population grew, but the number of brothels decreased and illegal individual prostitution flourished. Braila remained one of the big centres of prostitution in Rumania.

The prostitutes came from all social categories, but mostly from the poor social strata. Some of them were underage, others were married, while others practised prostitution alongside with their permanent jobs. Generally they were illiterate, but they were not alcoholics.

Looking at their economic situation, there were different categories of prostitutes. Brothels were the normal rule, but there can be made a differentiation. There were poor prostitutes who depended economically on the owner of the brothel; these prostitutes were cheap and their clients generally belonged to the poor classes. Luxury prostitutes were mostly illegal and they were very expensive. Depending on the place they frequented, their clients belonged to the rich classes. Some clients even paid for the prostitutes' living.

As for the ethnic origin of the owners of brothels and the prostitutes, we can say that most of them belonged to the ethnic groups of the Jewish, Hungarian, German, Russian and Polish. However, this ethnic origin of the prostitutes does not reflect the ethnic structure of the population of Braila, which is mostly of Romanian origin. That means that most of the prostitutes came from outside Braila and even from abroad. This situation was due not only to the fact that they were recruited by the owners of the brothels who had promised them jobs in the town, but finally got them to work in their brothels, but also to the (forced) mobility of the prostitutes (the clients of the brothels wanted new prostitutes).

The hygienical condition of the prostitutes was deplorable. The law in this case stipulated a strict hygienic supervision of brothels: the prostitutes were supposed to be medically examined twice a week. But in reality they were very rarely examined (only once in 5-6 weeks). This was done superficially and without the necessary equipment and carried out by an unqualified staff.

So prostitutes who were ill could go on receiving clients for some months. The provisions of the law were not obeyed because the punishments were not severe. As for the illegal prostitutes there was no hygienical control at all.

The authorities seemed to be indifferent to this problem, not being interested in supervising and controlling legal prostitution or to eliminate illegal prostitution.

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Authors: [Rudolf Atkale](#) [Carina van Rooij](#), Isha conference

Print Book, English, 1994

Edition: [View all formats and editions](#)

Publisher: Akalanka, Houston, 1994

Series:	ISHA journal, 2/94
Genre:	Congressen (vorm)
Physical Description:	IX, 310 p. ; 28 cm.
OCLC Number / Unique Identifier:	69147637
Subjects:	Congressen (vorm) Cultuurgeschiedenis

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